

Separating Assessment of Subject Matter Knowledge from Assessment of
Higher-Order Cognitive Constructs

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Clinical judgment is a classic example of a complex, higher-order cognitive skill. Clinical judgment is a decision made through a process that relies on healthcare knowledge and skills. Physicians, nurses, and other practitioners regularly use their knowledge and expertise to make decisions about complex, context-sensitive situations. These judgments have significant and often life-altering ramifications, making assessing for clinical decision-making ability an important part of licensure examinations for the profession. Good clinical judgment leads to selecting the best possible evidence-based solution after identifying and evaluating alternative care options, resulting in safe and effective care. A growing understanding of the need to assess cognitive skills such as clinical decision-making ability is leading test developers to search for ever-better ways to define and assess higher-order constructs (Epstein & Hundert, 2002; Muntean, 2012; Muntean et al., 2015).

The decision-making process that underlies clinical judgment includes multiple subcomponents, most of which are unobservable, and this increases the difficulty of assessing clinical judgment ability. Defining the construct of clinical judgment using a theoretical framework, such as a cognitive process model, allows measurement of the individual elements. This helps identify the point(s) in the underlying mental process where clinicians make errors in decision-making (for examples of decision-making process models, see Muntean, 2012; Busemeyer & Diederich, 2010).

Clinical judgment errors can occur because of a lack of prerequisite subject matter knowledge, because of faulty execution of the processes involved in decision-making to apply that knowledge, or both. For example, a clinician may know that shortness of breath is a sign of pulmonary embolism and may know that a person with a recent femur fracture is at increased risk for pulmonary embolism, but the clinician may fail to recognize that a patient who has a femur fracture and is short of breath may be experiencing a pulmonary embolism. This makes it important to disentangle assessment of clinician knowledge from

assessment of clinician decision-making ability. The following pilot study explores ways to assess clinical decision-making ability distinctly from clinical subject matter knowledge. More importantly, this study seeks to evaluate the assumption that subject matter knowledge is intrinsic to accurate clinical decision-making (Epstein & Hundert, 2002).

Assessing the Role of Knowledge in Clinical Decision-Making—a Literature Review

Decision-making researchers emphasize the importance of subject matter knowledge to making clinical judgments and assume that the lack of appropriate clinical knowledge results in suboptimal outcomes. For example, when outlining the cognitive processes involved in diagnostic reasoning, Elstein and Schwarz (2002) noted that diagnostic accuracy depends more on mastery of subject matter knowledge than on problem-solving techniques such as hypothesis testing. Similarly, Tanner (2006) explained how clinical judgments in nursing require various types of knowledge, including abstract knowledge, experiential knowledge, and contextual knowledge (see also Facione & Facione, 1996). More formally, Levett-Jones et al.'s (2010) clinical reasoning model explicitly incorporates knowledge through an information collection stage that sets the premise for clinical reasoning. The speculation that subject matter knowledge is intrinsic to good clinical judgment is prevalent throughout situational decision-making literature.

The relationship between knowledge and clinical judgment is not thoroughly investigated beyond the assumption that good clinical decision-making depends on subject matter knowledge, as outlined above. Unfortunately, this relationship is not often accounted for, and the failure to control for the clinician's knowledge poses problems for both licensure exams and experimental studies that assess clinical judgments. Specifically, without explicitly controlling for knowledge, it is unknown whether faulty or suboptimal clinical judgment is due to poor decision-making or lack of understanding.

Two popular methods used to assess higher-order cognitive thinking circumvent this confound. In the first method, researchers observe subjects in a simulated or actual clinical setting and evaluate them using a rubric that includes a measure related to the application of knowledge (Lasater Clinical Judgment

Rubric, Lasater, 2007; Mini-Clinical Evaluation Exercise, Durning, 2002; Kogan, Bellini & Shea, 2003). Rubrics of this type offer some success in teasing apart the contributions of knowledge to higher-order thinking. Unfortunately, they require observation and are not pragmatic for large scale licensure exams. The second approach avoids the issues of contextual knowledge altogether. Rather than measuring higher-order thinking within a domain, researchers assess general cognitive skills using tools such as the California Critical Thinking Skills Test (Gorton & Hayes, 2014; Bowles, 2000; Cisneros, 2009) and argue that they generalize across domains. Although performance on these general assessments is uncontaminated by one's knowledge base, it is impossible to capture the interaction between knowledge and higher-order thinking—and this relationship is quite important. As noted by Gillespie (2010), a clinician may have adequate knowledge but not have the ability to use it when making decisions because of underdeveloped thinking processes. The current pilot study is an initial attempt to account for knowledge in order to identify the source of errors in clinical judgment.

Theoretical Framework

Clinical Judgment

The various models of the clinical judgment process defined in the literature (for examples, see Dickison et al., 2015; Elstein & Schwarz, 2002; Levett-Jones et al., 2010; Tanner, 2006) share core ideas, including that: (1) A clinician recognizes cues that trigger the realization that a decision must be made. (2) The clinician forms multiple hypotheses about what might be happening and what should be done about it, generating a set of possible solutions, and then chooses the best solution. (3) The clinician takes action based on the solution chosen. (4) The clinician evaluates whether the chosen solution was successful.

The outcome of the clinical judgment mental process is observable, namely in the action the clinician takes. Hence, one proxy for assessing clinical judgment is simply to determine whether the clinician produced the correct course of action. However, this method may be unreliable, for example, when

clinicians take actions without thorough consideration of important factors. The clinician uses and builds upon a cognitive schema during the clinical judgment process (Benner & Tanner, 1987; Kahneman & Tversky, 1996; Facione & Facione, 1996). Clinical decision-making ability is a function of the clinician's knowledge and sensitivity to context (Gillespie & Peterson, 2009; Levett-Jones et al., 2010; Tanner, 2006). Thus, it is important to design assessments that expose the thought process that led to the decision outcome (Thomas, Dougherty, Sprenger, & Harbison, 2008).

Application of Knowledge within a Clinical Judgment Framework

Clinical judgment implicitly requires the application of subject matter knowledge throughout the judgment process. Table 1 presents an example of the several units of knowledge required to make a clinical judgment. In order to recognize cues, the clinician must know what environmental events to attend to (e.g., signs and/or symptoms of a problem). In order to judge options, the clinician must know the possible physiological causes of the observed cue and apply prior knowledge of the likelihoods of those possible causes. In order to take an action, the clinician must apply prior knowledge of the appropriate interventions for the identified problem. And finally, in order to evaluate outcomes, the clinician must know what to look for in order to verify whether the action taken resolved the situation.

Table 1. Clinical Judgment and the Required Knowledge Base

Clinical judgment step	Example of knowledge required
Cue recognition	Frequent coughing and a bluish color around the lips is not normal for this patient.
Judging options	Possible causes of these cues might be a foreign body that is partially obstructing the airway, a build-up of secretions, or a medication reaction. Given that the client has pneumonia, a build-up of secretions is the most likely cause.
Clinical action	Suctioning is an appropriate treatment for a build-up of secretions.
Outcome evaluation	Clinical signs of adequate gas exchange should be monitored, such as oxygen saturation level, respiration rate, and skin tone.

It is clear that domain-specific knowledge is required to make an adequate clinical judgment. This makes measuring clinical judgment ability challenging: Clinicians may make decision errors because of

faulty knowledge or faulty judgment—it is not possible to disentangle these sources of errors without further control. Thus, measuring and assessing general decision-making ability separate and apart from subject matter knowledge is important. This is what the current pilot experiment explores.

Methods

This study used the following classes of items that subject matter experts developed and that were used in a field test for a largescale licensure exam: (1) Knowledge questions, which only assess basic rote clinical knowledge; (2) Cue recognition questions, which explicitly assess one’s ability to recognize key aspects related to a clinical judgment problem; (3) Judging options questions, which explicitly assess the decision process of evaluating options, either competing hypotheses or actions; (4) Clinical action questions, which explicitly assess one’s ability to make a correct clinical action and, importantly, implicitly assess one’s clinical judgment ability; and (5) Outcome evaluation questions, which explicitly assess one’s ability to evaluate whether clinical actions were successful or unsuccessful. The example questions in Table 2 represent the kinds of test questions that were used in the actual study.

Table 2. Example knowledge/clinical judgment test question pairs

Clinical decision-making step	Knowledge question	Corresponding clinical judgment question
Cue recognition	Deep tissue massage is contraindicated for a patient a. receiving anticoagulant therapy* b. reporting a feeling of having “knots” in the muscles of the shoulders c. recovering from a muscle injury that occurred 5 days ago d. with hypertension	The massage therapist is talking with a client prior to providing deep tissue massage therapy. Which of the following statements by the client would require follow-up prior to the massage? a. “The right side of my lower back has felt stiff for about 3 months.” b. “I started taking a blood thinner for a heart condition.”* c. “My doctor says I have plantar fasciitis in both feet.” d. “I take a calcium and vitamin D supplement to help prevent osteoporosis.”
Judging options	Which of the following are potential adverse effects of massage? Select all that apply.	The massage therapist has received the following phone messages from clients. The therapist should first return the call from the client who a. received Swedish massage yesterday and is

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. nerve injury* b. internal bleeding* c. exacerbation of hypertension d. dissemination of infection* e. formation of blood clots 	<p>reporting soreness of the back and shoulder muscles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. received deep tissue massage of the back and abdomen therapy yesterday and is reporting feeling bloated and dizzy c. is scheduled for Swedish massage this morning but has developed a respiratory infection d. sprained an ankle while playing football one day ago and would like to schedule a sports massage for today
Clinical action	<p>Massage therapy should be avoided by clients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. with hypertension b. who are experiencing an exacerbation of rheumatoid arthritis* c. who have chronic lumbar pain d. with sciatica due to ligamentous causes 	<p>The massage therapist is talking with a client with rheumatoid arthritis who is scheduled to receive massage therapy today but is experiencing a flare-up of arthritis. Which of the following statements should the therapist make?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. "I will plan to use deep tissue massage to help relieve your symptoms." b. "Let's reschedule your appointment for a time after the symptoms have subsided."* c. "I will focus on massaging the joints that you find most painful during the appointment." d. "We will include active range-of-motion exercises as part of your appointment."
Outcome evaluation	<p>Signs that massage therapy has promoted relaxation for a client include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. an increase in heart rate b. a decrease in cortisol levels* c. an increase in blood pressure d. increased range of motion of joints 	<p>The massage therapist provided relaxation massage therapy to a client with an anxiety disorder 15 minutes ago. A test of the client's saliva cortisol before and after the massage showed a decrease in cortisol level. The client's resting heart rate changed from 134 before the therapy to 82. The massage therapist should</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. notify the client's physician regarding the saliva cortisol level b. position the client in a supine position with the legs elevated c. conclude that the therapy was effective in promoting relaxation* d. provide an additional 30 minutes of massage
<p><i>Note.</i> * indicates a correct answer.</p>		

In addition to the five item classifications, items across classifications were further matched on exact content topics. For example, a knowledge item and a clinical judgment item would be considered an exact match if they cover diet recommendations regarding a specific nutrient relative to a disease. Items

matched on exact content provided the best control for examining subject matter knowledge and its application via clinical judgments. Because one main objective is generalizing the results across a broad range of clinical topics, subject matter experts developed 270 items that spanned 54 topics.

The classes of items defined above were seeded into a larger pool of field test items. Because all items in the larger pool were randomly assigned to candidates, the current study employed a completely randomized fractional mixed design. Although the complete within-subject factorial design allows for the strongest conclusions regarding the relationship of the levels in, and among, each factor of the design, several pragmatic concerns prevented its implementation. First, the complete within-subject factorial design requires more field test items per candidate than possible given the constraints of the test. Second, assigning the required amount of items for the factorial on the exact same topic could produce unintended insight into the mental processes (i.e., constructs) and thus change candidate responding behavior. Empirically, this amounts to potential confounding artifacts that contaminate measurement (i.e., our results)—even when analyzed with models that attempt to capture local dependencies (e.g., testlet model, Bradlow, Wainer, & Wang, 1999). Therefore, given the constraints of the field test, the most appropriate design was a randomized fractional mixed design, where each candidate only encountered a random fraction of the whole experimental design. Although the entire experimental design was sampled, candidates only received a random subset of the levels/factors.

The purpose of this pilot study is to test four key hypotheses. Because items span a wide variety of clinical topics, *Hypothesis 1* states that (correct) responding probabilities differ across the clinical topics. Formally, we test Hypothesis 1 by constructing a model that contains a random effect for a clinical topic and comparing it against a model that omits the effect. The second prediction pertains to item type format. Subject matter experts wrote knowledge and clinical judgment items in two item type formats, multiple choice and multiple response. Results of our previous pilot work suggest that responding probabilities differ among these two formats. Accordingly, *Hypothesis 2* states that multiple response items are more

difficult to answer correctly. We test this hypothesis through model comparison by including item format as a covariate. To the extent that the item type format increases model fit, we retain it as a covariate in more complex models so as to prevent the effect from contaminating subsequent inferences.

Our predictions regarding items that assess the steps in the clinical judgment process are straightforward. Items that assess clinical actions implicitly require multiple clinical judgment processes, and because of this, there is more opportunity for committing errors in judgment. Because of this, *Hypothesis 3* states that the probability of responding correctly to clinical action items is lower than for the other clinical judgment items. Our final prediction regards the association between clinical judgments and the underlying knowledge. Those who make successful clinical judgments are very likely to have the required underlying knowledge. By contrast, having basic clinical knowledge does not necessarily mean that clinicians can apply that knowledge and engage in higher-order cognition. Thus, we predict an asymmetrical relationship between accuracy on clinical judgment items and accuracy on knowledge items. *Hypothesis 4* states that clinical judgment accuracy is a stronger predictor of accuracy of the underlying knowledge than the reverse relationship, where accuracy on the underlying knowledge predicts clinical judgment accuracy. Formally, we investigate the magnitude in predictors between two models that reverse the relationship between the predictor and the outcome variable.

Results and Discussion

The pilot study used a design that, for 3,100 examinees, administered a randomly selected knowledge item and its matched clinical judgment item from the set of 270 total items. This led to a final dataset of 6,200 total observations. The study focused on two main points, within-subject comparisons and generalizability across a variety of clinical topics. Sufficient sample sizes are required to draw valid inferences from the within-subject comparisons. Fortunately, each level of the clinical judgment factor (i.e., cue recognition, judging options, clinical action, and outcome evaluation items) had sufficient power for pairwise contrasts with knowledge items. In general, the analyses focus on the conditional

probabilities that candidates respond correctly to items that assess some higher-order cognitive skill, given they responded correctly to the items that assess the underlying knowledge. Collectively, these analyses help understand the relationship between domain-specific decision-making skills and knowledge.

Because generalizability is the other main focus of the pilot study, items were chosen to cover a wide variety of clinical topics. This resulted in using a large set of items relative to the number of observations collected. To increase power, topic difficulty was controlled by modeling it as a random effect, as is common practice in experimental psychology (e.g., Baayen, Davidson, & Bates, 2008; Judd, Westfall, & Kenny, 2012). To test whether this effect is significant and to address Hypothesis 1, that the probability of a correct response differs as a function of clinical topic, we carried out a likelihood ratio test. A null model consisting an intercept-only logistic model on binary accuracy responses (in/correct responses) was compared to an alternative model that included clinical topic as a random effect. Inclusion of the random effect led to a reliable increase in model fit, $\chi^2(1) = 61.75, p < 0.0001$, supporting the hypothesis that clinical topics differ in difficulty.

Similarly, we carried out a likelihood ratio test to investigate Hypothesis 2, that the probability of a correct response is lower for multiple response items than for multiple choice items. The simple model consisted of the intercept and the random effect retained from above and the alternative model included the item type covariate. Item type had a large and reliable effect, $\beta_{diff} = 0.84, SE = 0.10, \chi^2(1) = 71.74, p < 0.0001$, indicating that the probability of correct response is 5 times greater for multiple choice items than for multiple response items, supporting Hypothesis 2. Due to the large effect, we retained item type as a covariate for all subsequent models.

Hypothesis 3 pertains to the probability of correct responding to items that assess the four different clinical judgment processes. The likelihood ratio test revealed a significant main effect, $\chi^2(3) = 8.48, p = 0.0370$. Simple contrasts determined that the effect was driven by differences in correct

responding between items assessing cue recognition and taking clinical action, $\beta_{diff} = -0.36, SE = 0.11, p = 0.0068$, with examinees having a 44% lower probability of responding correctly to clinical action items. This lends support to our speculation that clinical action items are generally more difficult because examinees must engage in several distinct processes when responding to clinical action items. They must recognize relevant information, process that information to develop viable hypotheses, and then select an action according to the most likely hypothesis. The greater complexity brings about more opportunity for errors and thus manifests a lower probability of responding correctly. No other simple effect contrasts reached conventional significant levels.

Finally, we investigated the relationship between clinical knowledge and its application in clinical judgment items by constructing two sets of model comparisons. The first set of models investigates whether correct responses to knowledge items are associated with increases in correct responses to clinical judgment items, that is, whether clinical knowledge is a predictor of clinical judgment. A likelihood ratio test compared a full and simple model that differed on a single predictor, accuracy on knowledge items, and single covariate, item type of the knowledge item, to control for the effects of multiple choice vs multiple response item formats. This comparison revealed a reliable effect, $\beta = 0.18, SE = 0.05, \chi^2(2) = 17.35, p = 0.0001$, such that a correct response to knowledge items leads to a 20% higher probability of responding correctly to clinical judgment items. To test whether the probabilities differed across clinical judgment processes, an additional model was compared that included an interaction term (clinical judgment by knowledge accuracy). This revealed no increase in model fit, $\chi^2(3) = 0.34, p = 0.9523$, suggesting that clinical knowledge improves accuracy in the steps of the clinical judgment process equally.

The next set of models investigated the reverse relationship, whether correct responses to clinical judgment items are associated with increases in correct responses to knowledge items. Testing the symmetry in the associative relationship between knowledge and clinical judgment accuracy is

informative and of theoretical importance. Hypothesis 4 states that examinees may have clinical knowledge but necessarily the ability to apply it, and that if examinees are successful on clinical judgments, they are likely to have the basic understanding of the required knowledge. This prediction materializes in an asymmetrical relationship such that clinical judgment accuracy as a stronger predictor of knowledge than the reverse, and it implies that knowledge is a prerequisite of successful clinical judgment but that knowledge does not always lead to successful judgments. Switching the predictor and outcome variables in the above models, a likelihood ratio test determined that correct clinical judgment responses leads to a 46% higher probability of correct responses to knowledge items, $\beta = 0.36, SE = 0.09, \chi^2(2) = 15.72, p = 0.0003$, thus establishing an asymmetrical relationship. Examinees who make successful clinical judgments are more likely to have the underlying clinical knowledge, whereas those who have the underlying clinical knowledge do not necessarily make good clinical judgments.

Conclusion

Clinical judgment is a higher-order cognitive skill that is vital to successful performance as a health care practitioner; this makes assessment of clinical judgment ability an important domain of evaluation in licensure exams. Clinicians must employ both decision-making ability and an understanding of subject matter knowledge when making clinical judgments, and an error in clinical judgment may be the result of faulty knowledge, faulty application of that knowledge, or both. Determining the source of error in clinical judgment allows test developers to assess higher-order domain-specific cognitive skills uncontaminated by an examinee's knowledge base. The results of this pilot study supported two key hypotheses that allow us to further investigate the relationship between knowledge and higher-order cognition. First, the results suggest that there is a lower probability of responding correctly to test items that assess clinical actions than items that assess the other steps of the clinical judgment process. We interpret this result as evidence that clinical action items implicitly require higher-order cognition, which allows for more opportunity for error. Second, the results support the hypothesis that clinical judgment

accuracy is a stronger predictor of accuracy of underlying knowledge than the reverse relationship; clinicians who make correct clinical judgments are likely to have the subject matter knowledge required to make the judgments, whereas clinicians who have the subject matter knowledge required to make a judgment may not have the decision-making ability to correctly apply that knowledge. Collectively, the pilot study results serve as a motivation and a springboard for the development of a more rigorous clinical judgment assessment that controls for subject matter knowledge and context.

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